

A Book for Inquisitive Minds: A Voluntary Review of *Better Economics for the Earth*

Miracle Li

January 18, 2025

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There are two aspects to the book *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*: the intuitive, common-sense side and the complicated academic side. The main point of the book is easy to understand: humans are not the center of the universe, and to survive, humans need to respect the laws of nature. However, as an academic work by two university professors, this book is by no means a popular science article. It introduces many economic and physics terms and formulas, which can be intimidating for readers without a background in these fields. It will definitely put off young kids who enjoy fantasies, romances, or mysteries. The authors raise a very good point about efficient science communication: “Scientists should learn to step out of their comfort zones to write comedy, capture nature photography, and create personal creative writings.” Fables, satire, climate fiction, and eco-horror, as mentioned by the authors, might convey their messages more effectively to young kids and the general public.

This book is more suitable for those inquisitive minds who are willing to learn the theoretical side of environmental problems and try to understand the issue at a higher conceptual level. According to the authors, our reckless behavior and insatiable pursuit of economic growth have pushed Earth’s ecosystem to its planetary boundaries and humanity to the edge of an existential crisis. Using concrete numbers, the authors show us how serious our situation is regarding climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation. The authors criticize the mainstream neoclassical economics for equating growth with monetary gain, believing in perpetual growth on a limited planet, and relying on the miracles of innovation. They advocate for Eco surplus cultures to collectively tackle environmental problems. Several examples of wealthy celebrities living frugally are provided to demonstrate what we can do to help the Earth. I applaud the authors’ efforts to point out the flaws in our current economics theory and improve it by incorporating insights from physics, which is more general and not human-centered.

This book is professionally edited, and I cannot find a single grammatical error. I give it a rating of 4 out of 5. It is a great academic work, but it is not fun to read. It is for serious readers. For the general public, the book could be improved by incorporating elements of humor and using simpler, more accessible terms to introduce academic concepts.

Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories

by [Miracle Li](#) » 18 Jan 2025, 14:32

[Following is a volunteer review of "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories" by Quan-Hoang Vuong, Minh-Hoang Nguyen.]

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4 out of 5 stars

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Screenshot. Voluntary review of "Better Economics for the Earth" by Li [1] on Online Book Club.

(* Note: This paper reprints Li's review [1] appearing on Online Book Book Club. The title of the reprint was created based on the book review's content.

References

[1] Li, M. (2025, Jan. 18). Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories.

<https://forums.onlinebookclub.org/viewtopic.php?f=114&t=607783>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://books.google.com/books?id=I50TEQAAQBAJ>